

3: Gene Expression Omnibus Data to Fight Cancer

Systems biology and enhanced cancer diagnosis

With 4,348 datasets and more than two million samples, the [Gene Expression Omnibus \(GEO\)](#) shares and hosts microarray, next-generation sequencing, and other forms of high-throughput functional genomic data. Run by the US National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI), the repository allows biologists to find out how several kinds of cells look [from a molecular perspective](#). This is very useful, as knowing whether a gene is active in a cell is essential to know how to shape research.

The GEO platform

The platform is a priceless tool for researchers in the life sciences, as it allows them to upload their data for easy sharing with their peers. In addition, the GEO is an effective data management tool, as authors can upload their research data for safekeeping even before releasing them to the public along with their publications. The GEO also acts as a collaborative platform for authors and reviewers, as the data submitted can be accessed by various stakeholders for peer-review before manuscripts referencing them are accepted for publication in journals.

GEO data re-used

The biggest strength of the GEO lies in the fact that it allows data re-use and the development of new research. A Google Scholar [query](#) of “Gene Expression Omnibus” currently returns about

65,000 results, which shows the reach of the platform.

The research performed thanks to GEO data has an impact in various fields. One of the most promising is the [application of systems biology to cancer research](#), allowing scientists to understand how the networks of molecular interactions in cancer cells behave. While the mathematical and computational tools to understand these complex mechanisms could, potentially, have been developed in the past, the availability of data sources such as the GEO was essential to advance our knowledge on cancer. Understanding genetic networks allows a [prediction of the future evolution of cancerous cells](#), which, in turn, helps researchers in the pharmaceutical field understand how to design better anticancer drugs. This level of detailed analysis is enabling scientists to develop new treatment options that seek to modify individual proteins to halt cancer progression, or to modify the entire network of cells and reset it to a normal state, depending on the stage of the disease.

Other important cancer research exploiting the GEO platform relates to the way cancer progression is identified. As reported by [Nature](#), cancerous cells have been found to infect other healthy cells in the immediate surrounding tissue by shedding exosomes, which contain proteins, DNA and RNA. These exosomes then combine with healthy cells and cause the replication of cancerous cells, effectively infecting the healthy cell and spreading to new tissues. By tracking exosomes, disease can be tracked more efficiently than by isolating tumour cells floating

in blood, which are far less abundant. While this was just hypothesised in 2014, the approach **has reached the US market** in 2016.

Title	3: Gene Expression Omnibus Data to Fight Cancer
Subtitle	Systems biology and enhanced cancer diagnosis
Abstract	Sharing genomic data on the Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) repository has a significant impact on medical research and improves the efficiency of the publishing environment. New approaches to cancer research were developed, including a novel method of diagnosis based on the study of exosomes.
Keywords	medical research; cancer; repository; publishing
Research subject area	BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES
Type of RDM impact/benefit	Methodological impact (e.g., new approaches developed); Efficiency in research and data re-use (e.g., reduce duplication of effort)
Summary Impact Type	N/A
Facts and figures	65,000 results from Google Scholar
Original dataset from which the impact arose	
Maturity of the initiative/data source	Long-standing (5+ years)
Year (e.g., first data release, first output, year of impact)	2001
Organisations involved	National Institutes of Health
Academic citations	
Links	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/ http://www.nature.com/news/cancer-cells-can-infect-normal-neighbours-1.16212 https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3354560/ http://www.nature.com/nbt/journal/v34/n4/full/nbt0416-359.html https://bmcbioinformatics.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/1471-2105-10-S9-S1 http://www.nature.com/news/don-t-let-useful-data-go-to-waste-1.21555